

Developing Scientific Female Leaders in STEM: a Road Trip of Female Mechatronics Students

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Abstract

Participation of women in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) areas, have demonstrated to be crucial to develop a just, balanced and equitable society. In this work in progress paper, we present evidence of women inclusion in automatic control, robotics and technological based projects throughout the adequate project selection along their career progress. We worked with the challenge-based and research-based approaches, observing developing of skills such as increase of analytical analysis, complex thinking, logical thinking, innovation, collaborative work, organization and leadership.

Keywords: Women inclusion, STEM, female engineers, research-based learning, challenge-based learning.

1 Introduction

Inclusion of women in STEM areas at early ages is a crucial element in the design and development of an advanced society. This topic has become relevant in recent decades. Traditionally, STEM areas were dominated by men, leading to several society problems, such as professional gender disparities, gender barriers on STEM areas, bias in job opportunities, among others (Geetha, 2024; Jebesen, Nicoll, & Jayasinghe, 2022; Swafford, & Anderson, 2020). However, important efforts in the academic environment have been made to help to close the gender gap in STEM areas.

Academic institutions instrumented by professors, play an important role promoting the inclusion of women in STEM, throughout properly designed study plans, mentorship programs, hiring of female scientists and professors.

The inclusion of women in STEM is important for several reasons: diversity, economic empowerment, creation of role models for everyone as well as decreasing the gender gap, (Sevilla, Luengo, & Farías, 2023; Verdugo-Castro, García-Olgado, & Sanchez, 2022). In summary, the inclusion of women in STEM is not only a matter of fairness and equality, but it also leads to greater innovation, improved solutions to global challenges, and resilient economies.

The Tec21 educational model, implemented by Tecnológico de Monterrey since 2019 in its professional courses, is based on the challenge-based learning model. By solving real challenges linked to the environment, students develop disciplinary competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes and values necessary to practice a profession) and transversal competencies (developed throughout a career, useful for the life of the graduate, with impact on the quality of their work), which are demonstrated through the evidence of learning that students must present. This educational model consists of four fundamental components: challenge-based learning, personalization, inspiring faculty and memorable experience (Modelo Educativo TEC21, 2018; Olivares, 2021).

In this work in progress paper, we show a slight view of the vocational learning process of female mechatronic students in different stages of their engineering program. We will observe how female engineer students get

involved in the design and development of technology based projects and scientific research studies, increasing their analytical and logical skills necessary skills for the new century (Dinelti, Elizar, & Ali, 2007; Herlinawati, Marwa, Ismail, Dominikus, & Situmorang, 2024), by applying their knowledge and using pedagogical tools such as challenge-based learning and research-based learning, which are learning tools promoted by the Tec21 educational model.

2 Methodology

In this section we are going to describe the road trip of female Mechatronics students throughout their engineering program experience. We had observed how throughout projects and challenges they develop different skills than their peer male students.

2.1 Bachelor of Science in Mechatronics Engineering (BME)

The BME Program in Tec21 is formulated in eight semesters and it is based on training units. A training unit can be defined as a curricular space delimited in terms of content and time that can be implemented throughout four different methods: blocks, subjects, TEC weeks and TEC semesters. Also, a professional career in Tec21 is divided into three stages: exploration, focus and specialization. During the focus phase, mechatronics students are introduced into electronics, system characterization microcontrollers, mechanics and automatic control systems among others. The average composition of the group is approximately 80% male and 20% female students. In the following sub-sections, we present several cases of technological projects developed by female students of the mechatronics degree program in different stages of their career.

2.2 Learning Process

2.2.1 Fourth semester

Students start to work with system characterization, modeling an active suspension for an automotive vehicle. The main goal is to formulate the state space model of an active suspension of a $\frac{1}{4}$ with 2-Degree of Freedom (2-DOF) and $\frac{1}{2}$ with 4-DOF automotive vehicle. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Vehicle suspension assessed in the project.

They work with the following methodology:

- Research commercial solutions for passive, active, and semi-active suspensions.
- Research mathematical models of passive and active, semi-active suspensions for $\frac{1}{4}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ vehicles (reported in books and/or research articles).
- Obtain the mathematical model with differential equations for $\frac{1}{4}$ passive vehicle (2-DOF).
- Obtain the transfer functions for $\frac{1}{4}$ passive vehicle according to the outputs of interest (2-DOF).

- Through simulations, they evaluate the systems for different signal inputs.

Through this challenge, the female students developed analytical and complex thinking applying specific knowledge acquired in the subject. They demonstrated mastery of the topics covered in class, their analytical capacity, their ability to work as a team and self-management. For this challenge, it is proposed that two competencies must be achieved. Table 1 describes the competencies, and the evidence evaluated in this challenge.

Table 2. Competencies developed at a challenge reported in fourth semester.

Competencies	Description	Evidence
Fundamentals	Explains the operation of engineering systems and devices through structured and coherent arguments based on concepts, theories and principles of natural sciences, mathematics and computing.	Writing exam and oral presentation.
Integration	Appropriately applies mechanical, electronic, software and automatic control technologies taking into account specifications.	Writing report following the methodology explained above. This report includes simulation and validation.

2.2.2 Fifth semester

At this period students work on the design and develop the control systems, through out a training unit composed by, learning blocks and specific units. They work on the basis of the challenge-based learning tool. The challenge in this phase is to design and implement a mechatronic system for the automation of an industrial equipment or process. The system is implemented through the application of mechanical, electronic, software and automatic control technologies. The challenge may be linked to the manufacturing industry, the health sector or the commercial sector and will allow students to put their professional experience and personal talent at the service of others, to find solutions to economic, energy and environmental challenges through the use of technology. The following study case was developed by several students of the mechatronics program.

Students developed an automatic intensity control system for luminaires located in the university laboratory (see Figure 2); they worked with the following methodology.

- Input signal processing. 1. Place light sensors at strategic locations to monitor the available natural light. The sensors should have the capability to detect lux levels. 2. Position motion sensors at entrances or central locations to detect the presence of people in the laboratory.
- Luminaries' characterization. They obtained the mathematical representation of the actuators, by using the System Identification Tool from MATLAB.
- Control design. In basis of their knowledge acquired throughout the mechatronics program they designed and evaluated different automatic controllers for the actuator.
- They implemented the prototype and performed validation.
- Energy monitoring. They included energy metering components to monitor the energy consumption of the lighting system. This data could be used for optimization or analysis purposes.

Figure 2. Automatic control of laboratory luminaries' design.

In this challenge, female students show leadership, self-learning, management, collaborative work and effective communication skills as they are capable to implement the acquired knowledge in technological based projects. For this challenge, it is proposed that two competencies must be achieved. Table 2 describes both and presents the evidence with which it will be evaluated.

Table 2. Competencies developed at a challenge reported in fifth semester.

Competencies	Description	Evidence
Process characterization and validation.	Performs theoretical and experimental modeling of dynamic systems and handles graphic identification techniques of real processes based on the step response of the system. Perform experimental tests.	A report where the students describe the system characterization process. Validate the mathematical expression obtained for the physical system, throughout simulation tools.
Logical reasoning	The student evaluates her own and her team's reasoning, based on the logical elements that give greater certainty to, statements and assumptions, in her discipline.	Oral presentations in teams.

2.2.3 Sixth semester

At this stage, students have a sufficient domain in analog and discrete automatic control, mechanics, electronics and programming. At this semester they develop the design and implementation of a four degrees of freedom robotic arm with the following specifications:

- Degrees of freedom: 4
- Links: 2
- Joints: 4
- Repeatability: 10mm
- Payload: 200gr-300gr
- Working Range: 150 mm - 400 mm
- AC 120V Power Adapter
- Control at joint level

Students design and implement all the issues related to the robotic arm, from the mechanics, electronics, actuator characterization, control and forward and inverse kinematics design, as illustrated in Figure 3.. They follow the following methodology:

- Define system requirements and restrictions
- Mechanical design. This includes, material selection, effort analysis, among others.

- Selection of components (actuators, sensors, board)
- Control System Design. This includes forward and inverse kinematics, characterization of actuators, design and evaluation of PID controllers)
- Software development
- Prototyping and assembling

Figure 3. Design and implementation of an articulated robotic arm.

In this challenge, the students close a learning cycle in the automatic and discrete control area. They now have the tools to design, develop and integrate complex mechatronic systems. In addition to all the aforementioned skills, female students show greater abilities to integrate and lead work teams. It is also notable how the perception of their own capabilities is improved. For this challenge, it is proposed that two competencies must be achieved. Table 3 describes both and presents the evidence with which it will be evaluated.

Table 3. Competencies developed at a challenge reported in sixth semester.

Competencies	Description	Evidence
Develop mechatronic systems	Generates innovative proposals for a mechatronic system according to standards.	A report where the student reports the system design and evaluation, following the methodology explained before. The prototype
Assesses the technical and economic feasibility of a technological development.	The student is capable of evaluating the technical feasibility of a mechatronic development taking into account restrictions.	Technical report and oral presentation, where technical and economic feasibility were assessed.

3 Some differences between female and male student peers

Beside the technical competencies reported in Table 1, 2, and 3, female students have been observed to outstand on the following transversal competencies:

- Strong written and verbal communication skills for technical documentation and collaboration with team members.
- Ability to work effectively as part of a diverse team, understanding team dynamics.
- Mentoring junior engineers and take initiative on projects outside the curriculum. As we involve female students from advanced semesters as mentors of younger female students in some activities.
- Flexibility to face changing project requirements or workflows.
- Female students are prone to utilize more collaborative and consensus-driven approaches when facing problems, while male students may be more prone to individualistic solutions.
- Female students may adopt more conciliatory approaches to solve conflicts, while men students may be more direct or confrontational in their methods.

4 Conclusions

In this work in progress paper, we presented a slight view of the path of female students of the Bachelor of Science in Mechatronics Engineering (BME) program in the Tec de Monterrey. We placed special emphasis on the process of developing skills and competencies of female students, since the participation of women in STEM areas is crucial for the development of just and equitable societies. Where we also benefit as a society from the characteristics of female engineers, such as empathy, responsibility, inclusion and leadership that will lead us to a technological platform with greater innovation and development for everyone.

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